

EXPRESSIVES AS MORAL PROPOSITIONS IN MUNDARI

NATHAN BADENOCH
Kyoto University
 badenoch@cseas.kyoto-u.ac.jp

MADHU PURTI
Independent Scholar
 purtimadhu@gmail.com

NISHAANT CHOKSI
IIT-Gandhinagar
 nishaant.choksi@iitgn.ac.in

ABSTRACT

This paper discusses expressives in the Mundari language spoken in Jharkhand as moral propositions. Expressives have traditionally been peripheral to the study of language, but recently this class of words has started to receive more attention. Moving from a narrow conception of onomatopoeia, linguists have begun to discuss the idea of depictive language, in which sensory perception is communicated in vivid terms. The data in this paper are presented as an ethno-linguistic exploration of how expressives can have moral or ethical connotations, in addition to, or in some cases instead of, depiction of sensory perception. We argue that as moral propositions, Mundari expressives are part of the linguistic practices that create and recreate idealized types of social behavior, personal relations and cultural institutions.

Keywords: Expressives, Mundari, morality, sound-symbolism, linguistic ethnography

1. Introduction

Expressives (also called “ideophones”) have traditionally been peripheral for linguistic inquiry. They have typically been seen as iconic words that map sound to sense in a transparent manner. Thus expressives still continue in common language to be called “onomatopoeia.” However, this terminology does not cover the vastly complex semantic and pragmatic signification that expressives entail beyond the discussions of sound symbolism. In an early paper on the subject, Gérard Diffloth takes this fact of expressives into account when he argues for a semantic-based approach to differentiate the “expressive” domain of grammar from the “prosaic” (Diffloth, 1972).

Most recently the study of expressives has progressed beyond sound symbolism, with scholars like Mark Dingemans arguing that expressives are “marked words that depict sensual imagery” (Dingemans, 2012a, p. 655). The definition of expressives as depiction has allowed analysts to conceive of expressive meaning as a process of “showing” not “telling” (Haiman, 2018), different than the “descriptive” semantics of the prosaic lexicon. By grounding expressives in terms of sensory imagery, Dingemans has also created a paradigm for a universal typology of expressives on which one can organise expressives based on whether they depict auditory, visual, tactile, olfactory, or cognitive perceptions (Dingemans, 2012a). In this paper we suggest that the focus on expressives as a depictive proposition is limited due to its insistence on grounding expressive meaning primarily in sensory perception. This overlooks other aspects that the semantics encode, such as behavior, normative value systems, and ethical judgements. In this paper, we call these the “moral” aspects of expressive semantics.

Taking our examples from Mundari, an expressive rich Austroasiatic language spoken in Jharkhand, Odisha, West Bengal, and Assam states in India, we argue that expressives are indeed moral propositions. As we will show through a range of examples, their semantic range extends beyond the perception of sensual experience, to also include judgements that reference an operative value system in the society. In doing so we highlight how the aesthetic and ethical are intertwined in everyday activities, such as eating, cooking, walking, or conversing (Lambek, 2010).

We also build on Rumsey's notion of the ethical as implicated in the certain use of grammatical categories (Rumsey, 2010), adding expressives to person, mode, reported speech (Keane, 2010) and deixis (Hanks, 1990). As the academic discussion moved from a conception of aesthetics as separate from morality to one in which they are closely related (Guyer, 1990; Moore, 1995), Bateson had suggested in his 1968 paper "The Moral and Aesthetic Structure of Human Adaptation", that the two are differentiated simply by the logic that underpin them; morality is concerned with the codes that guide judgement, while aesthetic judgement is about the relationships that underpin them (Charlton, 2008).

Mundari expressives can have both positive and negative ethical implications. Of the many expressives depicting speech, we find both. For example, *taal-tuul* depicts skilled speech, particularly of people who are good story tellers. This refers to not only the fluency of the speech, but the ability to weave interesting and funny material into traditional motifs or make the experience pleasant for the listener. On the negative side, *paṭar-paṭar* depicts rapid, fluid speech that flows well, but is not intelligible to the listener. This often refers to people speaking Hindi, a prestige language that is indexical of the perceived sophistication and affluence of outside life, where someone is trying to impress others by speaking Hindi in a way that imitates city people.

Thus, expressives serve not only to show perception in the current moment, but also to frame future actions in terms of ethics. Expressives are therefore not only linguistic *icons*, showing resemblances between sound and meaning, but also *indexes* of certain idealized types of people and their behavior (Peirce, 1955). This indexical effect of expressives works together with their iconic, depictive features to serve as a potent linguistic resource through which Mundari speakers remind each other of right and wrong ways of conducting themselves in everyday life. In this paper we will cover "lifestyle" expressives, which include commentary on physical appearance and judgement on what behavior that appearance entails, expressives of wandering, and expressives of physical, mental and spiritual states. We also suggest that Mundari speakers employ expressives to mediate moral relationships between individuals and the community. Ultimately, we suggest that the expressive aesthetics of a language's grammar (Williams, 2014) is necessarily intertwined with the ethics and moral value systems of the speakers of the language.

2. Morality of expressiveness

As will be discussed in the following sections, the moral implications of expressive use can be very explicit in Munda culture. At the *buṛi-garasi* ritual that is held after the death of a relative, family members engage in a specific type of speech that is depicted with the expressive *siṛi-biṛi*. This is one of the many Mundari expressives concerned with the gossiping, telling secrets and speaking in graphic detail of relations between men and women. All of these have negative social connotations. During the ritual, participants say untrue things of an explicitly sexual nature about the spouse of the diseased. Talk of immoral behavior that is *siṛi-biṛi* is hoped to drive away the spirit of the diseased to leave the living in peace. The use of expressives is generally characterized as spontaneous and motivated by the direct experience of life, drawing on the speaker's interpretation of events. The performative representation utilises the sound-symbolism of expressive lexicon, and is located within a form of practice that takes on ritual meaning with larger community significance.

In presenting Mundari expressives as moral propositions, we build upon the growing body of ethnographic linguistic research conducted at the interface of grammar and poetry. Webster (2015) has analysed poetics of the Navajo language spoken in the southwest United States, and its "intimate grammar". He elaborates in this work how poetic treatment of the ugliness of a Navajo

reservation is an effort to get people to listen, think, see and then act and respond to the “problem” as it is described using expressive language. By using aesthetically pleasing language to address painful social and environmental issues, the poet is “doing something”. But the linguistic acts should be understood as calls for others to “do something” as well. Thus, moral judgement with real social implication is included in an act of expressive depiction within the intimate grammar of the language.

To illuminate the sound-symbolic element of this expressiveness, Webster provides background to speaking of “the ugly”. The expressive /-x-/ infix in Navajo had been described as augmentative, pejorative, intensive or depreciative, until Webster identified the moral force of the use of the velar fricative. But he moves us beyond a purely semantic discussion of degree or intensity; the difference between *chin* and *chxin* is not just a matter of intense description of dirt, but is extended to a social commentary of ‘dirt with grease, really dirty’, evoking a sense of loss of order in society. In the Navajo world, control versus non-control is a critical social distinction. Phenomena that are disagreeable in the sensory perceptual sense, as well as the social sense, are often marked with the expressive /-x-/ infix, to imbue the linguistic message with additional moral weight.

The Mundari expressive performance presented in this paper can be understood as a reflection of the intimate grammar that is shared by speakers. The use of expressives is, however, not just an articulation of a shared framework for interaction at a more direct level of experience across the human and natural worlds. It reflects a common way of thinking about these relationships, highlighting a culturally embedded “cluster of attitudes and beliefs about causation, nature and especially, how to communicate perceptions” (Nuckolls, 1996, p.15). When expressive language takes on an affective stance, offering commentary about social norms, it paints a landscape of ethics that not only “sounds like life” but also “feels like life” in all its social complexity. While the iconicity and indexicality of sound symbolism are rooted in cognitive processes of mimesis, the semantics of morally charged expressives can be understood as a type of linguistic methexis. Hearers are invited to participate in the performance, where sensory perception and social judgements are offered together in the context of community.

In her study of expressives in Pastaza Quechua, spoken in the lowland rainforests of Ecuador, Nuckolls writes “[s]ound-symbolic discourse aligns interlocutors not with a private kind of experience, but with socially shared perceptions that are cognitively salient” (Nuckolls, 2016, p. 14). In this paper we demonstrate how this cognitive salience relates further to the creation and recreation of social relations that support Munda ideas of community. Here, the world view that is encoded in expressive language is not only a diagram map of relationships, but roadmap for how this landscape “should” be navigated. The more prescriptive messages that are imbued in the description and depiction here are particularly vivid in Munda society in the area of Jharkhand, India, because communities are experiencing an intense period of change in which access to land, maintenance of cultural practices and relations with the wide range of Others bring pressure on social norms (Shah, 2010; Mullick, 2011). Historically, Munda are no strangers to social change, cultural adaptation and complex interethnic relations (Sen, 2018). It is not surprising that their language use reflects the concerns of the times, as will be seen in the examples presented below.

The use of expressives in Mundari thus must be considered in terms of the larger salient social contexts. Working from a solid, but semantically constrained foundation of glosses, we expanded definition to include the relevant nuances to Mundari expressives that appeared to be very similar in meaning. We were struck by the observation that a significant number of expressives were heavy in moral judgement, and decided to make a specific look at these words to see what sort of

messages were being delivered. We have been exploring different methodological approaches to eliciting linguistic data within an ethnographic setting that asks her to lead the discussion through her cultural landscape. Elsewhere we have described this as “performance in elicitation” (Badenoch et al., forthcoming). These moral nuances were not simply the product of narration in a specific social context, but were closely related as well to the sound-symbolic and morphosyntactic function of expressives in the Mundari language. The realisation that many of the perceptions communicated with expressives are negative in nature, usually referring to awkwardness in social relations - individual actions and how they contradict community bonds or represent a failure to uphold patterns of accepted, idealized behavior - pointed towards an intimate grammar, where the aesthetic meets the ethical.

Purti is a singer and story-teller, in addition to having collaborated with Mundari specialist Professor Osada Toshiki for over 20 years of linguistic work. The data and analysis are the result of her skills in story-telling and singing, which are reflected in this paper. Purti is a native speaker of Mundari and grew up in a Munda village in Khunti district, Jharkhand. The methodology used in this work was essentially a process of discussing the meanings of expressives, comparing with others, provision of stories and experiences in which these expressives had been used, and exploration of what situations they *could* be used in, and with what social implications. This was done as a part of the expansion and editing of the *Dictionary of Mundari Expressives (DME)* (Osada et al., 2019) that was carried out by Badenoch and Purti in 2017-2018. Early on, we realised that many of the meanings and examples she provided contained moral sentiment. In collaboration with Nishaant Choksi, who was working with us on a larger project on Mundari expressives, we directed the analysis towards a more ethnographic framework. The data and analysis necessarily include her own personal *commentary* on Munda society, which is in turn influenced by her experience living outside of the village and working closely with non-Munda and non-Indian researchers. It is likely that additional, and perhaps slightly different nuances, would surface for the expressives discussed below if discussed in the village. While we accept that this potentially a limitation to the current study, we do not find it to be a major problem, as the intent of our work is not to provide a map of Munda ethics, but rather to highlight an element of Mundari expressives that has not been discussed and contribute to our understanding of expressives more generally. As expressions of moral judgement, it would be expected that the content is open to discussion and argumentation among members of the community, and there would naturally be differing perspectives on the moral implications of such language use.

3. Mundari Expressives

Expressives are an integral part of Mundari linguistic culture, and are found in most all arenas of language use. As such, Mundari is firmly located within the South Asian linguistic area, proposed by Emeneau in 1956 as characterised by a number of shared structural characteristics including a rich repertoire of expressives. In addition to the prevalence of expressives in the languages of South Asia, it is striking how many of these words are similar in form and meaning across the different language families of the region. Thus the question of expressives within the history of the South Asian linguistic area is of interest. Expressives are pervasive within the Munda languages, meaning that their historical depth extends to the proto-language of that branch of Austroasiatic. The Austroasiatic languages of Southeast Asia, where most of the family is located, are rich in expressives as well, suggesting complex factors of inheritance and borrowing at work.

The formal aspects of Mundari expressives have been described by Osada (2008, 1992). This class of words generally uses patterns of reduplication and segmental manipulation to achieve the desired expressive effect. One component of our working definition of Mundari expressives is that

usually neither of the elements has meaning on its own. Four main formal types have been identified: identical reduplication, non-identical reduplication with segmental mutation, awkward formations and *-ken* formations (Osada, 2008). For example, identical reduplication has a (hypothetical) canonical *CVCV(C) base form copied in full as in *liṭib-liṭib* ‘light feeling of the heart beating’. The base form does not occur. Non-identical reduplication with segmental mutation can have either vowel or consonant variation in the reduplicated element - consonant mutation such as in *kuca-muca* ‘long and twisting’, or vowel mutation such as *kaba-kubu* ‘shuffling feet while walking, back bent and shoulders raised, like an elderly person’. Awkward formations, likely created in a process of expressive co-lexicalization that is now opaque to speakers, are less common, but still significant in the *DME*, taking a form in which neither element resembles the other such as *haṛe-gaja* ‘many things piled up in a room.’ The final type, *-ken* formations- in Mundari syntax *-ken* is an aspect marker - are derived from another expressive; for example *cirid-ken* ‘sharp, sudden feeling of topical pain on a certain part of the body’ is derived from *cirid-cirid* ‘sharp feeling of pain on the skin’. These formations generally denote quickness or suddenness, and are often transparent, in that the full reduplicated form exists separately. In this way, we can say that they are the only non-reduplicated expressives in Mundari, but are clearly derived forms.

The sound-symbolic aspects of the words are part of the core of expressivity. However, a full sound of segmental iconicity has not yet been elaborated in full. Looking at the lexicon of expressives, it is easy to see that /l/ in initial position often has the meaning of ‘soft’ or ‘swaying’, as well as ‘wet’ - *lupu-lupu* ‘motion of flapping or fluttering small wings’, *luṭu-puṭu* ‘appearance of skin that is blistered in many places’, *liyur-liyur* ‘flimsy or flexible surface that bends easily’, *logo-logo* ‘appearance of overripe fruit, begun to lose its shape’, *lem-lem* ‘slowly, smoothly flowing river’ and *lapur-lapur* ‘baggy clothes, flopping around the hands and feet’. The discussion below introduces *lidiṛ-pidiṛ*, denoting the softness of a fat body that jiggles when the person moves. This form is a variation of *lidiṛ-lidiṛ*, which denotes just the appearance of soft and fat. In this way, segmental mutation changes the nuance of the phenomenon being depicted, in this case contrasting between a state and a movement. In some cases, contrasting pairs can help identify the sound symbolism. For example, *biṛ-bor* depicts as tree growing straight and tall, but rigid and stiff; this is in contrast to *liṛ-lor*, which depicts something long and thin that is, or could be, swaying lightly back and forth. The contrast between /b/ and /l/ is the softness and potential for motion that allows bamboo to sway gently in the wind.

Semantically, expressives are both iconic, in that in the minds of speakers, the sounds have direct connection to the meaning, and indexical, because they point to idealised types in the natural and social world, as introduced above. Mundari speakers often use expressives metaphorically, and this is where we find overt linkages between the depictive and the moral. For example, *lumbud-lumbud* refers to the opening and closing of a bovine’s anus when it is defecating. Discussion of possible applications of this word led to the understanding that the most vivid imagery is when the cow has diarrhea, and the anus opens and closes repeatedly. The deeper exploration of this word was catalysed when it was mentioned that *lumbud-lumbud* can also refer to a person that cannot keep a secret and frequently shares information inappropriately with others. We postulate that the original meaning was the appearance of a hole opening and closing. The metaphorical linkages between a cow’s anus and a person’s mouth, both spewing things that are aesthetically not pleasant, highlight how sound, meaning and ethics are tightly intertwined. In *DME* we have provided this moral meaning as an accepted, conventionalised usage, but other expressives may be used metaphorically by speakers in situations that they deem appropriate. This type of usage is ripe for similarly playful semantic extension, because the expressive meaning may combine elements of sight, sound, motion and other sensory perceptions, as well as mental states and emotion (Badenoch, 2017).

Further elaboration of the sound-symbolic system will be left for another occasion, as we focus in this paper on the moral implications of expressive language use in Mundari. In the data presented below, we have written reduplicated morphemes with a hyphen in both the text and the interlinear glossing. The expressives are bolded in the interlinearisation to indicate that one reduplicated expressive coincides to the single EXP morpheme gloss. While this may be somewhat unconventional, it allows us to maintain the same notation throughout.

4. Lifestyle: Signs of appropriate living

Mundari has a wealth of words that depict the bodily condition of being fat. While being fat is not itself stigmatised in Munda culture, obesity can be the marker of a non-Munda lifestyle. The lifestyle of the ‘Other’, is represented by the term *diku*, which refers to the upper castes and non-Mundari speakers.

A common expressive for a fat person is *lede-lede* ‘sitting with a large stomach protruding’, but this is not simply a depiction of body type. Drawing on the sound symbolic // denoting softness, as briefly introduced above, in the following example *lede-lede* demonstrates the indexical relationship to a style of life associated with Diku merchants that have taken up residence in a Munda village.

- (1) *maṅḍoari-ko dukan-re lede-lede-oʔ-ge=ko dub-aka-n-a*
 Marwari-PL show-LOC EXP-PASS-EMPH=PL.SBJ sit-CONT-ITR-IND
 ‘The Marwari are sitting in the shop with their fat stomachs bulging out.’

The direct implication of this statement is that Diku stay in their shops, even though they may live in the village, sitting around making money off of Munda people. Many are vegetarians and eat a lot of ghee, which is a luxury, while Munda struggle to make a living from the fields and relish the chance to eat *jilu-utu* ‘meat dishes’. The indirect connotation is that Diku will not help other people in need, unless they are paid. The use of *ledeṅ-pedeṅ*, a derivation from *lede-lede*, to depict a bulging stomach evokes feelings about difference in diet, power imbalances and uncomfortable social integration. Judgements about attitude may be a part of the imagery.

- (2) *en hoʔo maṅḍoari-leka ledeṅ-pedeṅ-ta-n=eʔ sen-baʔa-i-a*
 That person Marwari-like EXP-PROG-ITR=3SG.SBJ go-here.and.there-EPEN-IND
 ‘That person is walking around like a fat Marwari.’

This usage implies that the person is fat, but more importantly that they are fat because of their lifestyle, in which they do not work like Munda and not participate in Munda life. A person described in this way would probably be putting on airs, boasting that they have a cushy life and do not have to work.

Related to the expressive *ledeṅ-pedeṅ* is *lidiṅ-pidiṅ*, the ‘appearance of fat person, stomach will jiggle if poked.’ This expressive is found in a construction such as

- (3) *lidiṅ-pidiṅ-ta-n=eʔ moʔo-aka-n-a*
 EXP-PROG-ITR=3SG.SBJ fat-CONT-ITR-IND
 ‘He is fat with a jiggling stomach.’

The use of the expressive with *moʔo* ‘fat’, provides not only a vivid depiction of the sensory perception, but can deliver a judgement about the cause of the fatness. An observation such as *moʔo-aka-n-a*, ‘she is fat’ is simply a statement about body type. Therefore, the question

- (4) *Japan-re cena-ko=m jom-ta-n-a. bese=m mofo-aka-n-a.*
 Japan-LOC what-PL=2SG.SBJ eat-PROG-ITR-IND. Very=2SG.SBJ fat-CONT-ITR-IND
 ‘What do you eat in Japan that makes you so fat?’

is a simply question about dietary habits, while

- (5) *Japan-re cena-ko=m jom-ta-n-a. lidir-pidir-ta-n*
 Japan-LOC what-PL=2SG.SBJ eat-PROG-ITR-IND **EXP-PROG-ITR**
bese=m mofo-aka-n-a.
 very=2SG.SBJ fat-CONT-ITR-IND
 ‘What do you eat in Japan that makes you so blubbery fat?’

includes a value judgement about the difference of the person’s easy lifestyle in a developed country, not having to do hard agricultural work, enjoying luxurious and copious amounts of food. This may also be a more pointed commentary on how the person is living like another. Expressives used in this way connote that perceived difference in lifestyles are not just a matter of physical corpulence or material wealth, but communicate feelings of resentment, jealousy and assertion of a set of community ethics associated with traditional Munda life. Here, the other can manifest itself as any non-Munda; the Diku as an affront to an idealised Adivasi way of life, the Japanese as representing a distant and prosperous country or a Western researcher that has the luxury of flying in and out of a research site without fully experiencing the trials of daily village life.

Mundari expressives of thinness are usually complex bundles of semantic material, referring to weakness, sickness and poverty.

<i>kayaη-kuyuη</i>	tall, thin, weak and unstable, said of the way a person walks
<i>nara-dura</i>	large but thin and weak body
<i>rakaηa-rakaηa</i>	thin body with bones protruding, hips and rib bones
<i>capa-cepo</i>	thin face, sunken cheeks
<i>caba-cubu</i>	thin, long legs without buttocks or waistline, walking awkwardly like someone on stilts
<i>jeηge-jeηge</i>	thin and irritable child, clings to mother whining
<i>raηku-jaηguηu</i>	tall and skinny walking with long strides

All of the above examples have negative connotations, but fall within the semantic range of the unmarked stative *usu?* ‘to be thin.’ They are however, not necessarily the direct result of the person’s actions or thoughts, and therefore are not what we consider here to be moral propositions. However, Mundari expressives for physically thin bodies frequently include the senses of filthy and poorly clad, which may carry social commentary on the cause of the poor state of personal affairs. For example, the DME defines *jerem-keηdem* as ‘thin, and dirty with ripped clothing.’ In our discussions of the meaning and usage of this expressive, it emerged that *jerem-keηdem* refers to not only the appearance of the physical state, but extends commentary on the personality or character of the person. A person described as *jerem-keηdem* would note evoke sympathy because the poor state of the person is considered to be that person’s own fault, including lack of work, lazy thinking or bad decision-making. Someone who is in a bad state of affairs, but with physical and mental capacity, could be told

- (6) *neka-ge=m tain-re do jaa mu-sinj jerem-kenqem-ta-n=em*
 like.this-EMPH=2SG.SBJ live-LOC TOP any one-day EXP-PROG-ITR=2SG.SBJ
rika-oʔ-a
 do-PASS-IND

‘If you keep living like this, someday you will be thin, poor and have tattered clothes.’

The implied message is that the person should start working, get back into “normal” daily life and do what they can to improve their situation. It is interesting to note that in this example, the prosaic stative meaning ‘thin’ is not used, indicating that the entire meaning is to be taken in its expressive sense (see example 2 above as well).

These expressives depicting fat and thin represent body types considered to be *not* normal for Munda people. They are linked by the theme of material prosperity. The extremes of *leden-leden* ‘fat’ and *jerem-kenqem* ‘thin’ are attributed to a way of life that is deemed not compatible with Munda cultural norms of hard work and community engagement. “Fat” is indexically related to notions of the modern wealth of the exploitative Diku other, while “thin” evokes images of poverty, weakness and the inability to meet the challenges of traditional Munda life.

5. Lost in life: Fate or failure?

People who lose their way in life are seen in two ways - some people are the victims of circumstance and bad luck; others bring on troubles because of their own doing. In the previous section, the moral judgement contained in *jerem-kenqem* was discussed in the context of people who have become destitute because of their own bad choices, not evoking sympathy. Someone who has lost their way in life, not sure what to do next is *lenqe-jere*. Things are not going well for a person and they get continuously weak from the lack of positive reinforcement. The person is the victim of bad luck, and can be described as *bilika* ‘worthy of pity’, and people will offer help to this person.

- (7) *ne hon-ko do kami-kami-te=ko lenqe-jere-caba-ja-n-a*
 this child-PL TOP work-work-by=3PL.SBJ EXP-finish-INGR-ITR-IND
 ‘These children were forced to work so much that they ran away forever.’

The children have become lost in life, as a result of relatives putting impossible pressure on them to do work that they were not familiar with, getting only criticism and ridicule. Because the parents have died, the children have become lost in life without anywhere to go.

If someone is referred to as *jala-kala*, this person has experienced multiple hardships and arrived at a point where they do not know what to do in life. This, however, is the result of bad decisions, bad attitude, and is not worthy of *bilika*. In contrast to *lenqe-jere*, people generally do not offer help to a person like this.

Similarly, *āya-bāya* describes a person who is physically lost, away from home wandering, not able to come back. Villagers do not know what happened to the person, but they are not sympathetic because the person made a bad decision. For example, a child born out of wed-lock may be run out of the village and disappear. But this is not worthy of *bilika* because the parents made a bad decision getting pregnant before marriage. Another example is three girls who decided to go to Delhi to find work, even though they did not speak Hindi. From the villagers’ point of view they were *āya-bāya* because going to the big city without the language is a risky and terrifying - and foolish - thing to do.

- (8) *cambari-kuṛi dili-saʔ-te kameni nanʒen=eʔ sen-ke-n-a.*
 Cambari-girl Delhi-side-to servant for=3SG.SBJ go-COMPL-ITR-IND.
en-saʔ-re ge=eʔ āya-bāya-ja-n-a.
 that-side-LOC EMPH=3SG.SBJ EXP-INGR-ITR-IND
 ‘Chambari went to look for maid work in Delhi and then became lost.’

Someone who has become lost *āya-bāya* may eventually re-find themselves and go back, but this depends upon both their decisions and luck. This is not the case for *dae-doe*, another situation of loneliness and lack of direction of life - for example, someone who has lost both parents, but neither of the grandparents want to take care of them. They do not know which side of the family to go to for refuge, aware of the fact that they will not be welcome in either place. They are not able to make the decision and feel hopeless. This is worthy of *bilika*.

- (9) *kaka-te-ta-ko muturi-kuṛi asam-ate=ko*
 Younger.uncle-his-POSS-PL Muturi-girl Assam-from=3PL.SBJ
au-li-ʔ-i-a, haga-te-ta-ko bese=ko
 bring-ANT-TR-1SG.OBJ-IND brother-his-POSS-PL very=3PL.SBJ
sadao-ki-ʔ-i-a. tayom-te do
 feel hard-COMPL-TR-3SG.OBJ-IND. Later-by TOP
kote-kote dāē-dōē-ta-n=eʔ rika-ja-n-a
 where-where EXP-PROG-ITR=3SG.SBJ do-INGR-ITR-IND.

‘Muturi was taken by her uncle from Assam, they made life so miserable for her that she left to wander all over and never returned.’

In this example, Muturi has been driven away by the bad treatment she received. It is understood that she did not really have any choice, so she will receive sympathy. Because she is so far from home and has been mistreated, it is impossible for her to make her way back; she has nowhere to return to. In contrast to *āya-bāya*, *dāē-dōē* is a problem of life scale. The moral imagery of *dāē-dōē* in this case becomes clearer in light of its more basic meaning: an unbalanced arrow falls *dāē-dōē* to the ground, fluttering around as it descends its directions unpredictable. A good arrow will fly straight to its mark, and a good life will consist of growing up, getting married, having children and living out one’s life in the village. Someone living *dāē-dōē* wanders around, unable to put down roots and establish one’s life, as expected by the community. This is a clear case of a metaphorical application of the expressive, moving from sensory perception to an assertion of an idealised type, where the original sensory perceptions are lost and the moral implications emerge.

Expressives of getting lost in life are clearly related to a person’s position within the community and their ability to manage the inside-outside tensions that complicate life at many levels, from the immediate to the extended family or from the village to the broader world. People who suffer from having left the comfort of community, for whatever reason, are recognized as experiencing trouble and hardship. Different circumstances, where it may or may not be appropriate to express sympathy, are reflected in the expressives used to depict the loneliness and despair of the lost person.

6. Physical beauty, spiritual protection and mental stability

There are several expressives depicting unkempt hair, many of which imply that a person does not take personal hygiene seriously. Other expressives for frizzy, kinky hair evoke feelings of

social awkwardness, or even danger. For example, the expressive *targal-turgul* ‘appearance of frizzy hair’ is not just a simple matter of curled versus straight hair, or even a question of cultural preferences for hair style. In Munda society kinky or frizzy hair is generally not preferred. As we probed deeper for more cultural context, Purti offered a song to help elaborate. The song included this stanza, including two expressives.

- (10) *boo?* ***ripi-ripi***
 head **EXP**
pita ***dalae-dalae***
 ribbon **EXP**
dinda-samae-re *kuɽi=m* *najom-an-a*
 unmarried-time-LOC girl=2SG.SBJ witch-CIS-IND
 ‘Frizzy head of hair
 ribbon swaying back and forth’.
 ‘Even as an unmarried girl you are learning to be a *najom*.’

Here, *ripi-ripi* is a seemingly neutral term for the appearance of tightly curled or kinky hair. The ribbon swaying back and forth *dalae-dalae* draws attention to the fact that the ribbon is not actually controlling the unruly hair. Upon further discussion, Purti explained that this type of hair was considered to be a genetic trait that indicated some sort of abnormality. Sometimes there is just one child among several who have *ripi-ripi* hair. If it is a girl, *ripi-ripi* hair is grounds for dismissing an arranged marriage, because it indicates that a child from the union may get it.

The concern about *ripi-ripi* hair is linked to the *najom* mentioned in the third line. The *najom* is a type of witch that causes people to fall ill, and is believed to have *ripi-ripi* frizzy hair. The *najom* is usually called *buɽia-najom* ‘old woman-*najom*’, as it is associated with elderly women. In the song, with the *ripi-ripi* hair, the girl looks like a *najom* although she is still young, indicating that there is something abnormal and potentially dangerous about her.

The ideal condition of a woman’s hair is *cuɽui?-buɽui?* straight hair - but more importantly, straight hair that is pulled back nicely and applied with mustard oil. This gives a clean and orderly look that reflects proper attention to one’s appearance. When the hair is not pulled back, it hangs around the face and sways with the person’s motions *daloe-daloe*, related to the *dalae-dalae* above. Because the hair is straight, there are no additional vivid nuances. If the hair is straight but tangled, however, and hanging at the sides of the head, the impression is of someone who is unstable or wild.

The reference to mustard oil is not simply a matter of sensory detail. In fact *cuɽui?-buɽui?* is only partially focused on the physical specifics of the slick, shiny, oiled appearance. The mustard itself is also an important factor of the affect. Mustard oil is applied for the proper look of well-kept hair, but it also provides protection against spirits - particularly the *buɽia-najom*, who will come at night to take people’s lives. In the Ramayana, when Sita was repelling the advances of Ravana she kept him at bay by throwing mustard seeds. When her store of seeds was gone, he was able to capture and take her away.

Thus the frizzy *targal-turgul* hair evokes a lack of the protection that is implied by *cuɽui?-buɽui?*. The appearance of the curls is iconic of the type of person that could become a dangerous *najom*. The normative message of *cuɽui?-buɽui?* is that women should take care of their hair not only because it is aesthetically pleasing and demonstrates that the woman is proper, but is a necessary precaution needed to take to protect oneself from bad spirits. It also demonstrates to a potential suitor that the girl is not *najom* material.

The expressive *taɾaŋ-buɾaŋ* is part of a semantic group of expressives denoting unpleasant countenance, evoking a feeling of suspicion or fear towards the person. Other members of this semantic group focus on buildup of body filth, darkness of skin and other physical characteristics, but do not have specific moral implications. For example, *gũĩ-gũĩ* depicts the dirty face or body of someone who has not bathed, with body filth gathered in layers. Although use of this word may entail a suggestion to clean up, there is no heavy moral judgement about the person's hygiene or economic standing, doing the work of Munda daily life involves getting dirty. Similarly, it is not common that people have multiple sets of clothes to wash and change into, so the physical appearance of *gũĩ-gũĩ* is a matter of non-judgemental observation.

The key element of *taɾaŋ-buɾaŋ*, however, is not wanting to look at the person's face. This is not because of the face's distance from sort of aesthetic ideal, but rather because the face has an unnatural, unsettled and disturbed look. Looking at the face puts the observer into a bad mood, or makes them feel uncomfortable. The unattractive look of *taɾaŋ-buɾaŋ* is the result of the person's actions, which have produced a situation in which they look haggard, intimidating or slightly wild. For example, a person who always drinks too much, may appear in an unattractive way during or after drinking sessions.

- (11) *en hoɾo jao-ge ili-arki nũ-nũ-a.*
 That person always-EMPH rice.beer-liquor drink-drink-IND
taɾaŋ-buɾaŋ-ta-n=e? lel-o?-a. lel-o ka
 EXP-PROG-ITR=3SG.SBJ see-PASS-IND see-also NEG
mone-i-a. sadaɾa ge=? lel-o?-a.
 want-3SG.OBJ-IND Dirty EMPH=3SG.SBJ see-PASS-IND
 'That person is always drinking and has a strange look on his face. I don't want to see him because he looks so dirty.'

The feeling evoked with this expressive is not limited to times when the person is drunk. Because the person is of that type, seeing them at any time brings the observer into that unpleasant state of mind. This type of person does not usually want to talk to others, does not have any signs of enjoyment and appears to be in an unnatural mental state. While cultural values concerning beauty abound in the vocabulary of expressives, *taɾaŋ-buɾaŋ* evokes feelings of social judgement about bad behavior. The personality of the person is reflected in the abnormal look on their face, and is indexical of the inappropriate behavior that causes it.

7. Expressives and imagination of the Self

Perceptions of Other in Munda life have been a common theme of discussion in the above. Mundari expressives also make more commentary on the perception and recreation of the Munda Self, with direct reference to ethnic categories, community identity and social cohesion. Social norms about appropriate behavior and relationships are based in ideas about the history of Munda village life and the coherence of the Munda as a people. Conceptions of Munda and non-Munda are most clearly articulated in relations with the Diku. In Mundari, *raɾi-baɾi* refers to the concept of mixed blood in a group of people. The lack of "purity" in bloodline is a perceived problem with the mixed blood of the Diku; in more concrete terms, it is said that the Diku themselves do not know where they came from and who they are (see also Shah 2010 for discussion of the concept of purity in contemporary Munda society). The Munda know where they are from and who they are because they are a cohesive, pure group. There is, of course, great diversity within the Munda social category. The Mundari have expressives to refer to the different types of speech of some other Munda groups.

When discussing the cultural connotations of *raṛi-baṛi*, Purti immediately gave a song:

- (12) *kuṭu-kaṭi* *muṇḍa-ko* *hae=bu*
EXP Munda-PL exclamation.of.pain=1PL.SBJ
reṅgeṅ-rabaṅ-ta-n-a.
 poor-cold-PROG-ITR-IND
raṛi-baṛi *diku-ko* *toa-maṇḍi=ko*
EXP outsider-PL milk-food=3PL.SBJ
jom-e-ta-n-a.
 eat-EMPH-PROG-ITR-IND
ote-aṛi *banoṅ-leka* *hae=bu*
 Land-hold nothing-like exclamation.of.pain=1PL.SBJ
reṅgeṅ-rabaṅ-ta-n-a.
 poor-cold-PROG-ITR-IND
ote-aṛi *menaṅ-leka* *toa-maṇḍi=ko*
 Land-hold exist-like milk-food=3PL.SBJ
jom-e-ta-n-a.
 eat-EMPH-PROG-ITR-IND
 ‘We pure Munda are poor and cold.
 The mixed Diku eat milk-rice porridge.
 We are poor and cold without field borders.
 They eat milk-rice porridge with field borders.’

There is a tension in the imagery of the Diku as an impure social group that is nevertheless warm, eating nice foods and having secure ownership over land. The use of the expressive *kuṭu-kaṭi* requires some discussion. A more precise translation of the term would be ‘original’, signaling that the Munda consider themselves to be indigenous to the area. It is likely that the term is a creative expressive usage derived from the term *khūṭ-kaṭi*, which is explained at length in the *Encyclopedia Mundarica* (Hoffman & Van Emelen, 2009) as a traditional institution for managing and protecting rights over Munda land. The semantic implications here are that the local, or original, land management system is not able to keep the more recent *raṛi-baṛi* Diku arrivals from taking their land. Thus the original Munda lead impoverished and insecure lives.

This song highlights some historical issues surrounding Mundari expressives in the larger South Asian areal context, concerning linguistic contact and change. It seems that *khūṭ*, which is a borrowing, as indicated by the aspirated stop, has been expressivised as *kuṭu*, a predictable form derived from reduplication of *kaṭi* with vowel mutation. The ambiguity shows how speakers play with expressives. More generally, it should be noted that the expressives used in Purti’s songs and sayings usually occur without any verbal morphology. In the examples taken from conversation and elicitation, most expressives take *-tan* and other grammatical morphemes, while *kuṭu-kaṭi* and *raṛi-baṛi*, in this example, are isolated from the larger syntax of the utterance. It is likely that expressives were historically outside of prosaic syntax, but were gradually integrated grammatically to take verbal morphology (Osada, pers. comm.), a process that usually is associated with decreasing expressivity (Dingemanse & Akita, 2017).

The next example, taken from conversation, shows how Mundari expressives still resist grammatical integration, possibly as a result of its specific sociocultural meaning.

Using the expressive *raṛi-baṛi* implies social confusion and lack of order. For example:

- (13) *en hatu-re do rari-bari jati-ko=ko tain-ta-n-a*
 That village-LOC TOP EXP jati-PL=3PL.SBJ live-PROG-ITR-IND
 ‘That village has all sorts of people mixed together.’

The expressive in this statement refers to a village comprised of people of different ethnicities and castes. This implies social turmoil because of the breakdown of community institutions. In specific terms, the Munda easily lend land to landless outsiders, and then are taken advantage of. Many people have lost land this way, because of the difference in ideas about land tenure and usufruct - the reference to the lack of field borders in Munda society. That is, they do not treat the land like individual property. When people are taken advantage of, it is often during drinking, where Munda are tricked into putting their thumbprint on a paper saying that they release the land to the Diku. When people are mixed in a village, there is also chance that there will be couples and inter-marriage, which will inevitably result in fights among the families. The loss of purity in the village, the result of outsiders with different history, thus brings about loss of land and women, and is plagued with conflict. Thus, the cultural affect of this usage is enhanced by the higher degree of expressiveness implied by the non-use of verbal morphology, as suggested above.

If the village speaks the same language, but there are different castes, it cannot be *rari-bari*, suggesting that there is some sense of ethnic awareness at play as well. For Munda, the three elements of purity are blood-lines (*jati*), language (*jagar*) and work (*kami*). The inclusion of work entails an agricultural lifestyle in which people cooperate and follow annual rituals. The expressive *hadda-huddu* provides insight on the norms of cooperation in agricultural work, and surrounding village cohesion more generally. At first, the meaning of *hadda-huddu* was recorded as ‘working together quickly and efficiently.’ Subsequently unpacking the details of usage, it emerged that the speed and successful result is secondary. The primary nuance is the feeling of working together in the fields; working together is enjoyable, as people usually tell stories and sing as they work. There is also a shared meal involved in the imagery evoked by *hadda-huddu*, sponsored by the person who is benefitting from the work-sharing that day. Consider this usage,

- (14) *nala-ko=le acu-le-d-ko-a. mu-sij-re-ge*
 day.labourer-PL=1PL.EXC.SBJ hire-ANT-TR-3PL.OBJ-IND one-day-in-EMPH
soben loyoŋ-ko hadda-huddu-ta-n=ko ir-caba-ke-d-a.
 all rice.field-PL EXP-PROG-ITR=3PL.SBJ cut-finish-COMPL-TR-IND
 ‘The hired work group worked together well and finished harvesting the field in one day.’

In this example, *nala* refers to a group of people mobilised to work together, a labor exchange group. The word *nala* is a short form of *jilu-nala* ‘meat-work group’, a work party that is not paid, but compensated by a meat meal. The other sort of work party is known as *kami-nala*, which is compensated with cash payment. In the case of a *kami-nala*, the work cannot be depicted as *hadda-huddu* because there is no enjoyable comradeship during the work and shared meal afterwards. In other words, the work is not a product of, or contributing to, the cohesive social relations of the village.

Contrasting *hadda-huddu* with other expressives for fast or efficient work, the moral weight of cohesiveness becomes even clearer. For example, with *uduŋu-duguŋu* ‘working quickly’, the context is simply hurrying to get something done, before a rainstorm or nightfall. On the other hand, *kurul-kurul* ‘working diligently at a task that requires a high level of concentration’, implies that the work is being done slowly and may not achieve its intent. In both cases, the concern is with the implications of an individual’s work, while *hadda-huddu* encompasses a larger social context of collective self in which work is conducted.

It should be noted in closing, that while *raṛi-baṛi* follows the trend towards expressivising negative social phenomena, the expressives for “good” work are examples of positive outcomes at the individual and group level. It seems that there is more moral weight on the *hadda-huddu* level of group cohesion and its implications for broader social relations. The positive moral judgement embodied in *hadda-huddu* demonstrates that social commentary through expressives is not limited to critique, but can be directly reinforcing of the ideals of cooperation, responsibility and solidarity that are lacking in the other expressives discussed above. These are the idealised conceptions of the imagined community embodied in definition of the Self and reproduced in the performance of moral expressives.

8. Conclusion

The larger social context of social cohesion is reflected in the moral propositions of the Mundari expressives examined in this paper, just a small selection of the large Mundari expressive lexicon. The expectation of participation in community life, contribution to a shared work ethic and maintenance of structured social relations provides an idealised prototype upon which actual behaviour is judged. As a matter of methodology, our ethnographic explorations of Mundari expressives and the moral material they carry touched frequently upon the question of whether the negative condition or state was worthy of sympathy (*bilika*). Would other Munda people be inclined to provide help to someone in that situation? For example, a person depicted as *jerem-keṅḍem* cannot be described as *bilika*, as this would suggest that the person is the victim of some bad luck or natural causes. As we have seen, this expressive denotes a cause and effect for which the individual is deemed responsible.

The affective stance taken when a speaker uses a morally-loaded expressive derives its force from the special semiotic content of this class of words. Description and depiction are translated into prescription, as the speaker engages the hearer in an exchange about reproduction of social conventions. For the Munda, language use is directly related to the passing on of the behaviors that are associated with cultural markers of Munda community. Purti concluded one of our work sessions with a song about people getting lost in life. This song teaches how people should develop in their social and linguistic practices.

- (15) *ne disum-tala-re* *isu* *re* *bai* ***jala-kala***
 This country-middle-LOC very INTERJ friend **EXP**
johar-e *itu-n-me*
 greetings-EPEN teach-REFL-2SG.IMP
sugaṛa-jagar-e *itu-n-me*
 beautiful-talk-EPEN teach-REFL-2SG.IMP
somae alo-m *lel-god-e*
 time PROHIB-2SG see-pluck-EPEN
seṇa *itu-n-me*
 wise teach-REFL-2SG.IMP
 ‘In this world there are many things that can confuse your path.
 Learn polite and friendly language,
 and don’t watch the world go by, gain wisdom for yourself.’

The use of *jala-kala* evokes imagery of a person that has lost touch with the experience and knowledge that should guide someone through life - another commentary on getting lost in life. If people do not know the social rules of language, such as respecting elders and welcoming guests, they will not be recognised by society; in other words, *jala-kala* is the result of failing to

develop understanding and competence through linguistic practice. This song is performed in a group dance, itself a bodily semiotic event that joins the aesthetic of group coordination and binding social norms.

While we find that Mundari expressives help speakers to engage in vivid depiction of sensory perception, these words can carry much more social nuance. We propose that in sounding like life (Nuckolls, 1996), Mundari expressives encompass commentary and judgements about complex and contentious aspects of social life as well. The conditions and situations that we find depicted with expressives are steeped in behaviors, personalities, decisions and expectations that play out in the specific details of Munda daily life. In addition to the examples introduced here, there is still a wide range of expressives commenting on gender roles, ways of speaking, begging, drunkenness, loitering, complaining, nagging, deviant behavior and many more. Even as expressive meaning moves further away from direct iconicity, the sound symbolism of expressives retains its power to coerce (Dingemans, 2012b) and seduce (Webster, 2017). Thus expressives actively communicate feelings of appropriateness across the embedded layers of individual and community, making uncomfortable crossings of imagined us-them boundaries and constructing intertwined cultural representations of the aesthetic and the ethical.

While it has been argued that human action is inherently ethical, this study of expressives has highlighted specific ways in which grammar is ethics, and ethics are grammatical (Lambek, 2010) in the Munda cultural context. Mundari expressives discussed above, examined within the cultural frameworks in which they are used, carry pragmatic weight that distinguish them from other expressives that are concerned primarily with indexical representations of sensory perception. As moral propositions, the examples described here indicate that expressives may contain commentary on social mores and cultural norms, encoded as judgements on the appropriateness of behavior, lifestyle, speech, gender relations, ethnic relations and agricultural work in the Munda cultural world. As indexes of an idealised Munda social world, these expressives are reflexively constitutive of “socially routinised metapragmatic constructs” (Agha, 2007) that are reproduced and reinforced through social commentary. This commentary makes use of the aesthetics of sound symbolism, metaphor and other forms of language play that bring interlocutors together to recreate community and negotiate cultural change. With the moral element, we expand the expressive function from verbal description and sensory depiction into the realm of social prescription, where Mundari expressives are performed at the intersection of grammar and poetry. We do not suggest that this moral-aesthetic entanglement is unique to the Mundari poetic imagination, but rather present this material with the hope that it will catalyse deeper ethnographic work on the rich and pervasive expressives of the languages of the South Asian linguistic area, and beyond.

COLOPHON

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ABBREVIATIONS

ANT=anterior, CIS=cislocative, COMPL=completive, CONT=continuous, EMPH=emphasiser, EPEN=epenthesis, EXP=expressive, IND=indicative, INGR=ingressive, INTERJ=interjection, ITR=intransitive, LOC=locative, NEG=negator, OBJ=object, PASS=passive, POSS=possessive, PROG=progressive, PROHIB=prohibitive, REFL=reflexive, SBJ=subject, TOP=topicaliser, TR=transitive, 1SG=first person singular, 1PL.EXC=first person exclusive

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